

DEGRADATION TO THE EXPLOSIVE BLAST RESISTANCE OF COMPOSITES DUE TO SEAWATER ABSORPTION

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ABSTRACT

The effect of water absorption on the explosive air blast response of composite laminates representative of the materials used in naval ships is investigated. The materials examined were woven carbon fibre-vinyl ester and glass fibre-vinyl ester laminates. The laminates were submerged in artificial seawater for increasing periods of time up to and beyond saturation. Subsequently, their deformation response when impulsively loaded by the airborne shock wave generated by an explosive charge was determined. The effect of increasing the peak overpressure and impulse of the explosive blast on the amount and types of damage to the laminates before and after seawater immersion was investigated. The amount of blast-induced damage sustained by the laminates was dependent on the types of fibre. The glass fibre laminate experienced much less delamination damage compared to the carbon fibre composites for different seawater immersion conditions. The deterioration to the blast resistant of both types of laminate was due to plasticisation of the polymer matrix and fibre-matrix interface, which reduced the mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced polymer composites are used in a wide range of applications where they are exposed to water, such as ships, submarines and offshore platforms. One of the advantages of using composites rather than many metals is their resistance to seawater corrosion. A disadvantage, however, is the loss of stiffness, strength and other mechanical properties of composites that may be caused by water absorption. Composites can be immersed or exposed to seawater for many years, during which time water molecules are absorbed into the polymer matrix and the fibre-matrix interphase region, which can reduce the mechanical properties. A potential problem with the absorption of water by composite materials (particularly as chemically bound water) is softening and damage to the polymer matrix and/or fibre-matrix interface [1],[2]. Absorbed water can reduce the stiffness, strength and other properties of FRP laminates due to plasticisation of the polymer matrix and fibre-matrix interface (e.g. [1],[3]-[7]). However, improvements can occur to some properties; for example, higher toughness and ductility leading to better impact damage resistance due to plasticisation of the polymer matrix [8],[9].

It is possible that reductions to the mechanical properties caused by water absorption will reduce the deformation and damage resistance of composites when impulse loaded by the shock wave generated by an explosive blast. The response of composite materials to explosive blasts has been extensively studied [10]. Virtually studies have been performed on 'dry' laminates or sandwich composite materials that have not been exposed to water or moist environmental conditions. Understanding the possible adverse effect of water absorption on the explosive blast response of composites used on naval vessels and offshore platforms is important.

Only a few studies have investigated the effect of absorbed water on the blast response of FRP laminates [11]-[14]. Gargano et al. [11] recently studied the effect of seawater absorption on the deformation and damage to a carbon fibre laminate exposed to air blasts. It was found that both the centre-point deflection and the amount of damage (e.g. delamination cracking) to the laminate increased with the amount of absorbed water. The reduction to the blast resistance was attributed by Gargano and colleagues to deterioration to the mechanical properties caused by water-induced plastification of both the polymer matrix and fibre-matrix interface. Schilling et al. [12] and Matos et al. [13] both found that the blast resistance of carbon fibre laminates were reduced following immersion in hot saline water (65°C). Similarly, Javier et al. [14] measured a reduction to the underwater shock wave pressure to cause failure of filament-wound carbon-epoxy tubes due to the absorption of water.

We aim to determine the effect of water absorption on the explosive blast response of vinyl ester laminates reinforced with glass or carbon fibres. The laminates are representative of the composite materials used in some naval ships, submarines, submersibles and offshore platforms. Vinyl ester was selected as the polymer matrix phase because it is commonly used in composite structures exposed to seawater due to its good durability and resistance to hydrolysis. Glass fibres are used because of their high strength and low cost whereas carbon fibres are often used for their high stiffness, strength and fatigue resistance. The laminates were submerged in artificial seawater for increasing periods of time up to and beyond saturation, and then their deformation response when impulsively loaded by an air shock wave generated by an explosive charge was determined. The effect of an explosive blast on the amount and types of damage to the laminates before and after seawater immersion was investigated. The results presented in this paper provide new insights into the effect of absorbed water on the response of composite materials to explosive blasts.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Composite Materials

The response to explosive blast loading of two types of laminate commonly used in ship structures was evaluated: woven carbon-vinyl ester and woven glass-vinyl ester composites. The carbon and glass used in the laminates were both single ply plain woven fabric (areal density of 600 g/m²). The carbon and glass fabrics were stacked into preforms with the warp tows aligned in the same direction, giving a cross-ply fibre [0/90] pattern. To ensure the laminates all had the same thickness (which was 4.2 mm), the carbon and glass composites contained 7 and 10 plies respectively. This small difference in the number of plies is not expected to affect significantly the response to blast loading.

The laminates were infused with liquid vinyl ester resin at room temperature using the vacuum bag resin infusion (VBRI) process. The vinyl ester (SPV 1265 supplied by Nuplex Composites) was catalysed using 0.8 wt% MEKP solution (40 wt% MEKP in dimethyl phthalate) (Norox from Nuplex Composites). Following the VBRI process, the laminates were allowed to gel and partially cure at ~20°C for one day, and were then post-cured at 80°C for one hour. The laminates were 4.2 ± 0.1 mm thick and had a fibre volume content of 50 ± 2%.

2.2 Seawater Immersion Tests

The laminates were fully immersed in a tank containing artificial seawater with a salinity content of 2.9% and temperature of 30 ± 1 °C. The laminate panels were withdrawn from the seawater at regular intervals to measure the change in mass. The panels were wiped dry using a lint-free towel to remove surface moisture, and then weighed within an accuracy of 0.1 mg to monitor the mass change. The percentage mass change of the laminate panel (M) was calculated using:

$$M = \frac{M_i - M_0}{M_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where M_i is the mass after a given immersion time and M_0 is the original mass.

2.3 Explosive Blast Testing

A schematic of the explosive testing of the laminates is shown in Figure 1. The targets were flat square laminate panels (275 mm x 275 mm) held within a rigid steel window frame (250 mm x 250 mm aperture). The frame was lined with soft rubber, which allowed the laminate target to flex freely

under the impulse load exerted by the shock wave. Before testing, the back surface of the laminate targets was painted white and then speckled with black dots to facilitate high-speed digital image correlation (DIC) measurements during the blast loading event. The dots were approximately 2 mm in diameter and spaced about 1 mm apart, which defines the spatial resolution of the DIC measurements. The DIC system was ARAMIS and used two high-speed Photron SA5 cameras operated at a frame rate of 7000 s^{-1} and offset at an angle of 22.5° (see Figure 1). The DIC results were used to measure the dynamic out-of-plane deflections of the laminate targets.

Figure 1: Schematic of the explosive blast test.

Spherical plastic explosive Type 4 charges made of RDX ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$ -1,3,5 trinitro-1,3,5 triazocyclohexane) were used in the blast tests. The charges were detonated using a 3.8 g EWB detonator (Type RP-80 produced by Teledyne RISI). The peak overpressure and impulse of the blast was increased by reducing the stand-off distance between the explosive charge and target and/or increasing the charge mass. The different explosive test conditions are given in Table 1, which includes the peak overpressure and impulse values of the shock waves. One sample of each type of laminate was tested in the dry condition for each blast test condition given. In addition, one of the laminates (glass-vinyl ester laminate) was tested three times under identical conditions (100 g of PE4 explosive at 0.4 m stand-off distance) to assess the variability of the blast loading response. The dynamic deformations did not vary by more than 5% between the three tests, and therefore any differences greater than this may be considered statistically significant.

The two laminates were also blast tested following immersion in the artificial seawater. The materials were blasted at a shock wave impulse of 463 Pa.s in air. Tests were performed on the laminates in the partially saturated, saturated and beyond saturated conditions, which are described later.

Explosive weight (g)	Stand-off distance (m)	Peak shock wave pressure (MPa)	Shock wave impulse (Pa.s)
100	1.0	0.63	109
100	0.8	1.30	154
100	0.6	3.36	219
100	0.4	10.9	353
160	0.4	16.0	463
200	0.4	18.0	500

Table 1: Explosive blast test conditions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Blast Response of Laminates in Dry Condition

The effect of increasing shock wave loading on the deformation response of the carbon and glass fibre laminates in the dry condition (i.e. before immersion in seawater) was investigated. The effect of increasing blast impulse loading on the maximum centre-point displacements for the laminates is shown in Figure 2. The maximum displacement increased at a similar rate for the laminates until a threshold impulse value (~ 220 Pa.s), above which the amount of deformation was influenced by the fibre reinforcement. The maximum deflection of the carbon fibre laminate was greater than for the glass fibre composite, and this difference became greater with increasing blast impulse.

The effect of increasing blast impulse loading on the amount of delamination damage sustained by the laminates in the dry condition is shown in Figure 3. The delamination damage area was measured from C-scan ultrasound images of the panels following blast testing. The ultrasound imaging was performed using two 2.25 MHz ultrasonic transducers, with one facing the laminate surface which was blast loaded and the other transducer facing the opposing surface. The amount of delamination damage in Figure 3 is defined as a percentage of the total surface area of the laminate target. Delamination damage to the carbon fibre laminates initiated at a shock wave impulse of ~ 220 Pa.s, and then increased in size with increasing blast impulse. In contrast, the fibreglass laminate showed no evidence of delamination damage, even at the highest blast impulse. However, this laminate experienced fine-scale matrix cracking and fibre-matrix interfacial cracking as did the carbon fibre composite.

Figure 2: Effect of blast impulse on the maximum centre-point displacement of the laminates.

Figure 3: Effect of blast impulse loading on the delamination damage area to the laminates.

3.2 Water Absorption Behaviour of Laminates

The effect of immersion time in the artificial seawater on the percentage mass change of the laminates is shown in Figure 4. The curves show an initial linear increase in water uptake over the first five-to-six months (expressed as the square root of time) after which reached a steady-state weight gain. This trend is indicative of Fickian-type water absorption into the laminates. The rate of water uptake was not dependent on the polymer matrix, although did differ between the glass and carbon fibre reinforcement. The carbon laminate reached maximum moisture content after ~5 months immersed in artificial seawater, whereas the glass laminate required ~6 months reaching the same level of saturation. The peak plateau weight gain of the glass and carbon was similar, at ~0.2% total mass gain.

The carbon laminate was withdrawn after 20 days (half saturated), 5 months (saturated) and 15 months (well beyond saturated) for mechanical property and blast testing. The glass laminate was withdrawn after 1 month (half saturated), 6 months (saturated) and 18 months (well beyond saturated) for testing.

Figure 4: Measured weight change-seawater immersion time curves for the laminates.

The mechanical properties of the laminates in the dry condition and after immersion in the artificial seawater for increasing periods of time are presented in Figure 5. The properties measured were the flexural modulus, flexure strength, compressive failure stress and interlaminar shear strength. All of the properties were degraded by the absorbed water, and this agrees with other studies for fibre-polymer laminates immersed in water (e.g. [1],[3]-[7]). The deterioration to the mechanical properties is attributed to plasticisation of the polymer matrix and weakening of the fibre-matrix interface. The colour of the fibreglass laminate was also changed by prolonged immersion in the water. For example, Figure 6 shows the glass laminate surface in the dry, half-saturated and beyond saturated conditions. This laminate experienced increasing discolouration (darkening) with increasing water immersion time, and this is attributed to a deterioration of the polymer matrix phase. (Similar discolouration to the carbon fibre laminate panel by the absorption of seawater was not observed visually due to the dark colour of the carbon filaments).

Figure 5: Mechanical properties of the laminates for the dry and different seawater immersion conditions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6: Surface of the glass fibre laminate in the (a) dry, (b) half-saturated and (c) beyond saturated conditions.

3.3 Effect of Absorbed Water on Blast Response of Laminates

Centre-point deflection against time curves measured for the carbon and glass fibre laminates in the dry and seawater immersed conditions are shown in Figure 7. A positive displacement in the curves means that the centre-point of the laminate panel is deflected in the same direction as that of the shock wave propagation, and a negative (convex) displacement is when the panel is moving towards the source of the explosion. The laminate panels began to deflect with the arrival of the shock wave (~0.15 ms after detonation of the explosive charge) and deformed in the wave direction. The panels reached a peak deflection value, and then in some cases deflected back towards the source of the explosion. The amount of deflection experienced by the panels was increased by the absorption of water. The peak deflection of the carbon fibre laminate was ~50 mm (or ~100%) greater due to the absorption of water. The maximum deflection of the glass fibre laminate was less at about 10 mm (or ~25%) more due to the water. While the absorption of water led to loss of out of plane stiffness and hence increased the deflection experienced by both laminates under shock wave loading, there was no clear correlation between the amount of water absorbed and the increased deflection of the laminates.

Figure 7: Centre-point displacement vs post-detonation time curves for the (a) carbon fibre laminate and (b) glass fibre laminate subject to an explosive blast. Curves are shown for the laminate in the dry, half-saturated, saturated and beyond saturated conditions.

Macroscopic photographs of laminate panels in the dry condition and different seawater immersion conditions following blast testing are presented in Figure 8. The thin white regions on the carbon fibre panels indicate where the carbon plies have ruptured under the shock wave loading. The white regions in the fibreglass laminate indicate regions of delamination cracking. Both types of damage initiated at the edges of the panels and propagated rapidly towards the centre-point location. All of the carbon fibre laminate panels sustained ply rupture, however the number of rupture lines increased with the immersion time in seawater. This can be attributed to the reduction in the mechanical properties of the laminate caused by the absorbed water, particularly the significant reductions in the failure strength.

Following blast testing, the laminate panels were non-destructively inspected using through-transmission (C-scan) ultrasonics to determine the amount of damage. Ultrasound images of the laminate panels before and following blast testing are shown in Figure 9. The blue regions indicate where the laminate panels have sustained delamination damage, which completely attenuated the ultrasound signal. The ultrasound images show that the surface area of the laminate which contained delamination damage increased with the seawater immersion time, particularly for the carbon fibre composite. The images also show that the blast caused more damage to the carbon fibre laminate compared to the glass fibre composite.

Figure 8: Damage patterns in the carbon fibre laminate (upper) and glass fibre laminate (lower) panels in the dry, half saturated, saturated and beyond saturated conditions following explosive blast testing.

Figure 9: Ultrasound images of the carbon fibre laminate (upper) and glass fibre laminate (lower) panels in the dry, half saturated, saturated and beyond saturated conditions following explosive blast testing.

4 CONCLUSION

The mechanical behaviour of carbon and glass fibre laminates to explosive blast loading is degraded by the absorption of water. For the vinyl ester laminates studied here, the water uptake behaviour for both laminates follows Fickian-type diffusion. The carbon fibre laminate absorbed water at a faster rate than the glass composite, although their equilibrium weight changes were similar. Before seawater absorption, the glass fibre laminate was more resistant to blast-induced damage compared to the carbon fibre composite. The resistances of the laminates to deformation and damage were reduced by the absorption of seawater, and this is attributed to the reduction to the mechanical properties caused by plasticisation of the polymer matrix and fibre-matrix interface. The blast resistance of the carbon fibre laminate was reduced more by the absorption of water than the glass fibre composite. The results for both laminates reveals that the blast damage resistance of composites used in seawater environments, such as naval ships and submarines, can be degraded significantly by the absorption of water.

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